

AID to DATA ~ Digital Archiving and Transformed Analytics -- Advanced Integral Digitalization via Machine Learning Automata

S. Liang, E. MacCarthy, C. Hall, and P. Gardner

Lane College¹, Jackson, TN

A. Abstract

Advanced Integral Digitalization (AID) aims to liaise with universal interface, aggregate intelligent browsing around Anything-as-a-Service (XaaS), and engage with user-centric experience throughout digital archiving and transformed analytics (DATA). AID-to-DATA proposes a panel tutorial in a CIA triad framework with ease to *Contextual expression*, *Interactive engagement* and *Accessible emergence* from wiseCIO.

The AID promotes a CIA triad framework for ACTiVE applications with *contextuality* that promotes universal (user) interface design (with little coding), *interactivity* that engages with user-centric experience, and *accessibility* to archival content management and delivery (ACMD) via machine learning automaton (without coding). With AID, we have developed a set of hybrid online courseware utilized in hands-on learning throughout tutorial sessions. Case studies through XaaS have been explored and exploited with DATA over broad fields, such as ARM (archival repository for manageable accessibility), BUS (biological understanding from STEM), DASH (deliveries assembled for fast search & hits), DIGIA (digital intelligence governing instruction and administration), HARP (historical archives & religious preachings), MATH (mathematical apps in teaching and hands-on exercise), and SHARE (studies via hands-on assignment, review/revision and evaluation).

The AID not only promotes *interactivity* among tri-parties (such as developer, user and computer) but also prompts *spontaneity* for the user's patience and passion for their subjects (such as researchers & developers, instructors and students, and librarians as well). As a result, AID propels integral DATA to propagate student users to retain the knowledge conveyed with a known attendance rate increase from 50% to 90%. This proposed tutorial will share educational excellence emerging from wiseCIO. The AID-to-DATA combination plays a key role in hybrid online courseware that fosters learners' patience and passion with AWE -- Appreciation for knowing what to learn, Wonderment at how to be excellent, and Excelling through their studies.

B. Keywords

AID: Advanced Integral Digitalization

DATA: Digital Archiving & Transformed Analytics

wiseCIO: web-based intelligent service engaging with Cloud Information Outlet

ACTiVE: accessible contextual traceable information for vast engagement

ACMD: Archival Content Management & Delivery

C. AID-to-DATA is relevant to following topics

¹ Coding & Creativity (C²) Partnership with Apple & Tennessee State University

- Architectures, frameworks, and technologies for science gateways
⇒ AID represents the architectural framework for web-based intelligent service
- Support for scalability and data-driven methods in science gateways
⇒ DATA fulfills SUBA (scalable ubiquitous browsing automation) throughout data-driven transformational automation.
- Science gateway usability, portals, workflows, and tools
⇒ wiseCIO orchestrates Anything-as-a-Service (XaaS) via Advanced Integral Digitalization / DATA
- AI and ML for science gateways
⇒ OMLa (Open Machine Learning automaton) promotes AID-to-DATA

D. Outlined Plan & Resources for Tutorials (90 minutes)

	Summarized tutorials:
	a. Proposed tutorial length: 90 minutes (maybe 3 hour?) A possibility to extend to 3 hours, depending on needs
	b. Recommended skill level: MS Word & computer/PC operating
	c. Technology & Software Requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A browser well connected with PC/Laptop/Tablet/iPAD, ... - Accessibility to wiseCIO, the platform for tutorial - A personal account of Google Drive or gmail - [optional] part of personal information (name) for mock exercise ...

A panel presentation on AID-to-DATA by team (30 minutes)

A panel presentation by the tutorial/instructional team members will be conducted to present how AID has been built under the CIA triad framework through:

- Digital archiving via **Contextual** Expression, **Interactive** Engagement, and **Accessible** Exploration/Exploitation. This represents UI & UX with little coding
- Transformed Analytics via Machine Learning automaton (MLa) to automate UI & UX design in a detail-oriented approach with no coding required AT ALL. A set of MLa rules are provided as FAST ingredients that are feasible, analytical, scalable and testable. The DATA is illustrated in the sampled slide as follow:

This panel presentation regarding AID-to-DATA starts with the most essential questions to be answered throughout the presentation, such as

Q1: How easy is it to express UI with web design on wiseCIO?

Q2: How easy is it to engage with hybrid / hands-on learning over DATA?

Q3: How easy is it to explore / exploit web content in depth / breadth?

C-eye for AID: Advanced Integral Digitalization!

Q1: Is it easy to express UI with web design?
⇒ user interface design with little coding

Q2: Is it easy to engage with hybrid learning?
⇒ hands-on exercises via step-by-step

Q3: Is it easy to explore content in depth?
⇒ user-centric experience (CIA)

□ **2-4 instructional (breakout) sessions** for audience (35 minutes)

The instructional sessions will be arranged via breakout meetings, and each session consists of 5-10 participants depending on how many audiences have interest in such kind of tutorials that they will be able to experience wiseCIO (an advanced platform for XaaS) and engage with Advance Integral Digitalization for their needs.

Each participant will have a profile or biography account (proBIO) so that the individual can have an inspirational trial, hands-on exercise, and applicable iPPP (instant Presenting / Programming / Publishing) as shown below:

Three hands-on exercises will be offered as follows:

- Initial import of proBIO for customizable needs in support of a new websection to be created within less than one minute.
- An Essay on TRIAL: the hands-on exercise is used for participants to write an essay that illustrates the acronym, such as

Try / **R**enovate / **I**nnovate / **A**dvance / **L**ove

So that the webVersion will be formed and published onto the individual's proBIO. And based on the webVersion, the user can create Word Doc from his own Google Drive to be published (via iPPP) on to his proBIO for accessibility with ease.

- A collaborative scheduling worksheet: the hands-on exercise is designed for use of multiple & 3D sheets to excel participants with the magic number 7 ± 2 utilized to control the complexity and applied to task management.

This hand-on and hybrid exercise also help to disclose the user / participant that individual Google Drive becomes individual's remote space that is ACTiVE (accessible, contextual, traceable information for vast engagement)

A 5 minute break

Innovation via review & renovation

Instructional innovative outcomes through the tutorial section will be published via DATA on wiseCIO for further review, renovating, and innovating.

C-eye for AID: **A**dvanced **I**ntegral **D**igitalization

AID to DATA Empowering us with “strong arms” in digital age

E. Reference

(1) DATA: Digital Archiving and Transformed Analytics ([IIM Vol 13 No.1, Jan 2021](#))

(2) wiseCIO: Web-Based Intelligent Services Engaging Cloud Intelligence Outlet ([Intelligent Computing Vol 1 SAI 2020](#))